

Unpacking The Benefits and Challenges in Utilization of Laptops in Grade 7 TLE Curriculum

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to describe the experiences of grade 7 students in the utilization of laptops in the implementation of the TLE 7 curriculum at Sto Niño High School, Tanjay City Division, school year 2024-2025. The study employed a purposive random sampling technique where seven Grade 7 students were qualified based on the selection criteria made by the researchers. Moreover, phenomenology was used as a methodical approach in the study. The gathering of data was situated at the school library at the participants' preference and convenience. An audio recording was ethically practiced during the interview for credibility purposes of the data. Thematic analysis was utilized to generate codes and themes. Upon a rigorous analysis, three major themes emerged. These are first-hand experiences, technical supervision, and worthwhile experiences. Students' first-hand experiences comprise varied feelings such as inhibitions, fear, worries, and excitement at the same time in using laptops. As a result, the teacher's guidance played a significant role in teaching and implementing the TLE 7 curriculum. Despite the challenges and difficulties, they faced and the help of the teacher, participants had worthwhile experiences such as being motivated and active in classroom sessions where they interacted and presented their works creatively. Thus, the study suggests that in the utilization of laptops and other mediated technology tools, teachers should be equipped with the skills and knowledge in terms of content, pedagogy, and technology as emphasized in the framework of TPACK to effectively deliver the learning objectives of the curriculum.

Keywords: *Qualitative research; phenomenology; lived experiences of grade 7 students in utilization of laptops in TLE 7; benefits of using laptops*

Introduction

Technology has completely changed the lives of people. It has touched various aspects of life and has redefined life. Undoubtedly, technology plays an important role in all areas of life. One of the amazing products of technology results in easier and faster application of mankind. In the landscape of education, technology is utilized to aid the teaching-learning process. Digital technologies are now working as knowledge providers, information producers, teachers, and evaluators. Advances in technology have made life easier for students, replacing the traditional pen and paper with computers and tools to create presentations and projects. Digital devices such as the iPad and e-books provide simple and practical alternatives to heavy notebooks in research.

In the current digital era, laptops become a necessary tool for students to use in their academic endeavors. Integrating technology into the curriculum offers teachers a valuable chance to improve student involvement and academic achievement. Using digital platforms, students can work together with classmates, utilize technological tools to foster creativity, participate in higher-level cognitive processes, engage in learning through inquiry, integrate information from various sources, and create a sense of social presence in the online environment (D'Angelo, 2018). According to the study by Raja, R. and Nagasubramani P. C. (2018), new insights into how today's students are better at using technology and how it affects their learning if they use technology, it is found that using new technology and tools, student learning and interaction are increasing. They also find it more interactive and fuller of interesting spaces with the help of technology. The exchange of knowledge becomes very simple, meaningful, and effective. Although there are many advantages to using laptops in the classroom, there are drawbacks as well (Ullah et al., 2024). The ease and versatility that laptops provide is one of the main advantages of using them in the classroom. With laptops, students can access a wealth of information quickly, which makes it easier for them to

conduct research and finish assignments on time. Furthermore, laptops facilitate note-taking, essay writing, and presentation creation, helping students maintain productivity and organization. People from many walks of life now consider laptops to be an essential tool. From portability and convenience to increased productivity and communication, they have several advantages. A laptop may make your life easier and more satisfying, regardless of whether you're a professional, student, or just someone who likes to keep connected. Using computers in the classroom also has the benefit of encouraging student collaboration. Students can collaborate on group assignments, share documents, and interact online with their peers with ease when using laptops. This may result in heightened interest and a more thorough comprehension of the subject matter being studied (Herold, 2022). In addition, the use of laptops by students can aid in the acquisition of vital technical skills necessary in the current employment landscape. Through the utilization of laptops for academic purposes, students can attain competence in software such as Microsoft Office, Google Docs, and PowerPoint, all of which are widely utilized in professional environments. This could provide students with a competitive advantage as they transition into the workforce post-graduation (*Advantages of Technology in Education for Students* | Varthana, 2024). The way students learn has been changed by technology, which has made education more interactive, engaging, and personalized. However, according to the study of GeeksforGeeks (2024) despite the many benefits of using computers in education, there are also challenges to consider. One of the biggest challenges is the risk of compromise. With access to the internet and social media, students may be tempted to engage in non-curricular activities in class, which may disrupt their learning experience. Additionally, there are concerns about the digital divide, where students from low-income families may not have access to computers or the Internet at home. This can disrupt educational opportunities and hinder the success of these students. Schools and policymakers must address this issue by providing the necessary tools and resources to ensure equal access to technology (Cappola, 2020). Aside from this, the geographical location of the learners also influences the availability of devices and the knowledge of how to use all of these. Most of the students who are living in the hinterland do not have access to laptops and cell phones due to the lack of income from their parents which hinders them from using those devices (Torres, 2024).

Technology helps people in so many ways but if not used appropriately, it will yield undesirable results. In this case, the framework of TPACK, or technological pedagogical content knowledge was introduced by Punya Mishra and Matthew J. Koehler in 2006. The concept of TPACK makes a clear point of understanding toward the use of technology in teaching. In this framework, the success and effectiveness of teachers' employment of technology largely depend on the knowledge he/she has of the content of the lesson and the knowledge of pedagogical methods in the teaching-learning process. However, if teachers do not have the capacity and skill to employ these devices, the goal to succeed in the implementation of the curriculum will be jeopardized (Kurt, 2019). Thus, students' learning will be at stake. Based on the literature above, both positive and negative effects can be the result of utilizing technology-mediated materials in the implementation of the curriculum. What matters is the importance of the experience that the learners have in the learning process. Experience plays an important role in the learners' learning. According to the theory of the Cone of Experience introduced by Edgar Dale in 1960. Dale's method was predicated on the notion that when learners "do" instead of using "hear," "read," or "observe," they hold onto additional information which makes the pace of learning effective (Prajapati, 2023).

In this sense, the present study aimed to investigate the lived experiences of grade 7 students on the utilization of laptops in implementing the TLE 7 curriculum at Sto Niño High School, Tanjay City Division, school year 2024-2025. Through the lens of phenomenology, the study sought to address the following questions.

1. What are the lived experiences of grade 7 students in using laptops in TLE?
2. What is the meaning of their experiences?
3. Based on the findings, what recommendations can be made?

Methodology

This section elucidates the research design, locale, participants, instrument, data gathering procedure, and appropriate consideration of the study.

Research Design

Phenomenology is a study methodology that aims to capture the essence of a phenomenon. by examining it from the viewpoint of individuals who have experienced it. Determining the significance of this experience, both in terms of what was experienced and how it was experienced, is the aim of phenomenology (Throop, 2024). In the context of the present study, the researchers used this design to view the lived experience of grade 7 students in the utilization of laptops in TLE 7 at Sto Niño High School for the school year 2024-2025. Using thematic analysis, codes and themes were produced to drop brightness on their experience.

Research locale

Selecting a suitable research location is crucial for setting the scene and comprehending how local influence could affect the study's conclusion and take away a part made from the study. It is necessary to select a location that is appropriate for the purpose and objectives of the study (Macam, 2019). In this context, the research locale of the study is at Sto. Niño High School Library. This site is located near a grade seven classroom where the participants are studying since they chose it for their convenience.

Research Participants

Research volunteers are vital to the field of study because of their capacity to provide researchers with priceless knowledge and data, assist in gathering information, and formulate conclusions for a range of appropriate research experiments, surveys, and interviews. The researcher used a purposive sample strategy in this investigation. Purpose sampling, commonly known as expert or judgmental sampling, is the researcher's purposeful selection of participants based on their areas of expertise. Participants are chosen specifically to meet the study's objectives rather than individuals who may participate in a survey directly or indirectly through a representative and provide their consent (*Ethical Research Involving Children, ERIC, Child Ethics, 2024*). Participants were carefully selected based on the following criteria set by the researchers a) he/she must be a grade 7 student b) officially enrolled at Sto. Niño high school for the school year 2024-2025.

Research Instrument

A research instrument is a tool used to gather, measure, and evaluate data from subjects related to the study topic (*Instrument, Validity, Reliability, 2018*). The researcher used open-ended questions from the interview guide used in this study to help with the subsequent unstructured interview. Additionally, the researcher trained a student interviewer to conduct one-on-one interviews with participants to ensure confirmability and personal bias (*Types of Bias in Research at Different Stages | CW Authors, 2022*). In this sense, the researchers prepared a consented audio recording of the participants' verbatim responses. Moreover, the interviewer was adaptable when it came to providing questions to get better results. For credibility purposes, the trained student went back to the participant. This is to ensure that the ideas during the individual interview are consistent with the participants' meaning and to check if the participant has any additional information that he or she may have forgotten during sharing. The student interviewer did this for each interview session. That is why it was necessary to hold this meeting to ensure the accuracy of the data.

Data gathering procedure

Data collection techniques are crucial to qualitative research to get a thorough understanding of the specifics of human experience and behavior. Pre-, during-, and post-data collection are the three methods being used in this study to collect data. The researchers invited the participants to an orientation during the pre-data collection phase, where they discussed the purpose and importance of the study. Additionally, data privacy was stressed, and the informed consent distribution came to pass. It was also emphasized that because participation in the study is optional, participants may leave at any time. As a result, the researchers started collecting data after eight sessions were completed to saturate the data. All the data gathered from each interview was meticulously documented by the researchers. Additionally, during the post-data collection stage, researchers transcribed, examined, and categorized codes to produce themes from all the data they had gathered.

Ethical considerations

Ethical considerations are crucial for protecting the safety and rights of participants in qualitative research. By following ethical guidelines and principles, researchers can create a courteous, transparent, and fair study process. Ultimately, ethical considerations sustain the integrity and dependability of qualitative research. In this study, the participants' identities were kept confidential. It was made possible by coding. Furthermore, it is guaranteed that all information and data gathered for this study will be kept completely private and for research purposes only. Moreover, as stated in the researchers' informed consent, participation is voluntary, and participants can withdraw anytime. Thus, with the cautious review made by the schools' review board, it certifies that no rights have been violated.

Results and Discussions

This section presents the study's primary findings. The lived experiences of grade 7 students in using laptops in the TLE curriculum at Sto Niño High School. These experiences were highlighted through the development of codes

and themes using thematic analysis. Table 1. Thematic map of the lived experiences of married people participating in sports programs in Barangay Sto. Niño, Tanjay City, Negros Oriental in the year 2024.

Table 1: Thematic map of living experiences of Grade 7 students on the utilization of laptops in TLE 7.

CODES	THEMES
It was not easy for the first time It's hard when you don't have experience Things are unfamiliar Arrow is gone and they don't know how to revise Pressing the wrong button Difficult in learning the password Hard to enlarge the letter Difficult to open and shut Difficult to make PowerPoint presentation Scared that the laptop will break Scared that the laptop will fall Excited at the first time but found it difficult Difficult to hear the voice of the teacher	First-hand experience
Not used to using laptops Need the guidance of the teacher Always asking questions	Technical supervision
Motivated to participate in class discussion Volunteers to demonstrate in the class Making works creative Helping students stay focused on the discussion Feeling confident Feeling active	Worthwhile experiences

First-hand Experience

In this digital age, laptops have become a necessary tool for students. Easy access to information, flexibility in the classroom, tools for content creation and presentation, interactive learning opportunities, and tools for efficiency and organization are all provided to students. Students may boost their academic performance, improve their learning experience, and set themselves up for success in school and beyond by making the most of their laptops. Based on this theme, grade 7 students experience varied emotions including inhibitions, excitement, and expressions of difficulties. These experiences made them undergo the initial stage of learning basic computer skills in the implementation of the TLE 7 curriculum. This is supported by the participants' responses.

Participant 1 said, "I accidentally pressed the wrong button on my laptop and I'm not sure how to fix it. I'm worried that I might have broken something. The interface is unfamiliar to me, and it's hard to make the text larger".

Participant 2 added, "I'm terrified that I dropped the laptop and broke it. I also experienced it shutting down unexpectedly, leading me to believe it was damaged. I admitted that I was unfamiliar with how to open it, especially since it was my first time using it. And to top it off, I'm finding it difficult to enlarge the text and the screen."

Participant 3 mentioned, "I initially pressed the home button and found myself unable to return to Microsoft Word. The arrows on the screen disappeared too! I'm excited to use the laptop but a bit scared because it suddenly shut down. I also having trouble typing the password and creating a PowerPoint presentation.

Furthermore, participant 4 mentioned, "I accidentally pressed the wrong button and am unsure how to undo the action. I also worried that he might have damaged the laptop. He added that he's struggling to open and close the device, enlarge the text, and type his password."

Participant 5 shared, "I was initially excited about the laptop but quickly found it challenging, particularly when I'm trying to create PowerPoint presentations.

Participant 6 also shared, "I am struggling initially, unsure how to open the laptop because the interface was completely unfamiliar. I also noticed that the arrows on the screen disappeared, and I didn't know how to get it."

In addition, participant 7 added, *"I am afraid that the laptop is broken because I might drop it. I also experienced the laptop shutting down unexpectedly, which made me nervous because I thought it might be damaged."*

In this theme, mixed emotions were felt by the participants as they expressed their responses. Upon utilizing laptops, participants encountered feelings of excitement and inhibitions. It was their first time using a laptop, so they were not sure what to anticipate, leading them to commit mistakes. Despite being excited and curious, they inevitably felt worried that they might press the wrong buttons and miscarry the laptops. This consequence is manifested by their first-hand experience as part of the initial stage of learning. Thus, the role of the teacher is vital to facilitate learning in the classroom.

Technical Supervision

To make sure that students acquire the abilities and information needed in the employment of technology in implementing the curriculum, technical supervision from the teachers is imperative. In the context of this study, participants encountered various challenges pinned in their firsthand experiences. These include frequent asking questions and instructions on the technical steps needed to use laptops. These experiences impede the pace of the teaching-learning process in the classroom if not catered by the facilitator. Consequently, these struggles called for the teacher's supervision as the participants expressed.

Participant 1 said, *"It wasn't simple at first, so I needed my teacher's help whenever something went wrong with my laptop, like the arrows disappearing or I didn't know how to turn it off."*

Participant 2 added, *"Since I'm a student and am afraid of using a laptop for the first time, I usually ask our teacher for advice and am worried about what I'm going to do because everything is new to me."*

Participant 3 mentioned, *"It's hard when you don't know, so I always ask my teacher questions like how to emphasize the letter and how to type."*

Participant 4 shared, *"I always need the guidance of my teacher because I don't have any experience in using a laptop. And at first, I don't know how to put the password."*

Furthermore, participant 5 said, *"As we try new things it is not easy at first, I always ask question to my teacher what I am doing to do."*

In addition, participant 6 said, *"I don't know what I am doing at first, so I need the guidance of my teacher when I am using the laptop then suddenly the arrows are gone, and I don't know how to revise it."*

Lastly, participant 7 said, *"I need the assistance of my teacher because it is my first time using a laptop and all things are unfamiliar."*

The theme highlights how difficult it is for Grade 7 to use laptops. Due to their lack of knowledge and expertise, the participants require direction from their teachers. The process of monitoring and directing individuals or groups to make sure their work complies with the lessons' objectives, standards, and best practices. When it comes to fostering professional growth and improving performance, supervisors are essential in offering guidance, criticism, and support. Students benefit greatly from laptop use monitoring since it provides guidance on appropriate behavior. Students who still find it difficult to utilize computers & require assistance in learning how to do so will find great benefit in the coaching. Under the framework of TPACK, the learners' success in using technology depends on the teachers' content knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, and technology knowledge.

Worthwhile Experiences

In today's modern environment, using a laptop has become an essential element of the educational process. Laptops have completely changed how students study and interact, from taking notes in class to doing research for assignments. In the utilization of laptops in the implementation of the TLE 7 curriculum, it is inevitable to experience challenges along the way. However, despite these struggles, participants' motivation is positively affected by the students' engagement in using laptops. They become confident, focused, and socially active in classroom interaction (May 2024). Being able to have the confidence to volunteer makes learning productive. This idea is substantiated by the participants' responses.

Participant 1 said, *"I know how to make a PowerPoint presentation, and I feel like I know so much."*

Participant 2 added, "Our paper is well organized, and it is interactive. I always like to use laptops in every class."

Participant 3 mentioned, "I can make our report more creative, and we can easily print our notes".

Participant 4 shared, "I am not ignorant in the digital environment anymore. I am thankful for this strategy that our teacher employed."

Furthermore, participant 5 said, "I can see that my classmates are having so much fun, and we are all fascinated by using laptops. This allowed us to do our work and reports in a presentable and creative manner."

In addition, participant 6 said, "I love to use our laptops because it's different when we do not use them for our lessons. I can observe that all my classmates are having a good time every time we use laptops. Everyone becomes active".

Lastly, participant 7 said: "Because of this, we were allowed to expand our knowledge in using technology-mediated tools. Our class is even more exciting due to this opportunity".

Using laptops as a technology-mediated tool in the implementation of the TLE 7 curriculum posed various emotions, particularly at the students' end. Although it may sound challenging, using laptops while learning in TLE 7 gave them an avenue for discovery and self-improvement. As emphasized by the participants, they felt motivated to learn due to the new way of learning the lessons especially since they are living in an environment that lacks educational resources. Moreover, the atmosphere in the classroom becomes a positive vibe and inviting due to the increased chances of showcasing their creativity in making outputs, presentations, and reports. All these worthwhile experiences contribute to achieving an objective and effective curriculum implementation in TLE 7.

Conclusion

Based on the findings, the study revealed three major themes namely first-hand experience, technical supervision, and worthwhile experience. It is concluded that grade 7 students experienced mixed emotions such as inhibitions, fears, worries, and excitement on the utilization of laptops in the TLE 7 curriculum as manifested in their first-hand experience. Although these challenges were evident, the role of the teacher was imperative for technical supervision. It was necessary for the teacher to constantly guide the students for better results and effective class instruction and interaction. Furthermore, despite the difficulties and mixed emotions they felt in using laptops in their lessons in TLE 7, the participants' emotions and motivations toward the subject were adjusted gradually as they continually used laptops in their lessons. It was evident that grade 7 students demonstrated active participation in the class discussion, and their creativity was fostered through the knowledge they gained from the guidance of the teacher. Thus, upon thorough analysis, the study suggests that in the employment of laptops in implementing curriculum, it is a need that teachers must be equipped with the pedagogy and methods appropriate to the learners' needs to promote effective teaching and learning processes. Research-wise, the study recommends that future researchers focus on teachers' competence and methodologies in the utilization of technology-mediated tools in the implementation of curriculum and its effects, influence, or relationship to the student's performance in a particular subject area.

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